

Several shortcomings in the meta-analysis on vitamin C and COVID-19 by Xu et al (2024)

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Comment on:

Xu W, Wang P, Wan J, Tan Y, Liu Y, Chen Q, Zheng Y, Yu X, Fan S, Jorge Luis CD, Zhang Y. **Effect of vitamin C supplementation on outcomes in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis.**

Front Nutr. 2024 Oct 3;11:1465670.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39421622>

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2024.1465670>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11484096>

Xu et al. [1] published a meta-analysis aiming to analyze the effect of vitamin C on outcomes for patients with COVID-19.

Specificity is crucial when evaluating evidence for any intervention. To assess the effect of vitamin C, comparisons should isolate vitamin C against a control, rather than testing vitamin C in combination with other substances. However, Table 1 [1] included 3 trials in which vitamin C was not the only difference between the compared groups. This concern is well-founded – not speculative – as two of the studies administered vitamin C together with vitamin E, while the large ATBC Study demonstrated that vitamins C and E can interact in their effects on mortality [2]. If the research question is specifically about the effect of vitamin C on COVID-19, then only trials testing vitamin C alone should be included.

Figure 2A [1] provides very strong evidence that the trials are not estimating a single, common effect, as indicated by a highly significant test for heterogeneity ($P < 0.0001$). Given this strong evidence of heterogeneity, the average effect is meaningless. As an analogy, if the occurrence of breast cancer in a population is calculated without stratification by sex, the average rate is meaningless. When there is significant heterogeneity, the focus should be on trying to determine the causes of the heterogeneity, and not on calculating the overall average which is irrelevant.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

In Figure 2A [1], the study by Adhikari et al. [3] is by far the largest; it accounts for 79% of the deaths in the figure (727/924). However, for clinical reasons, Adhikari et al. analyzed the data separately for critically ill patients and for patients who were not critically ill, whereas Xu et al. pooled the heterogeneous patients into a single analysis.

In Figure 2A [1], Xu et al. calculated that mortality increased in the vitamin C group of the Adhikari trial (RR = 1.29). However, it was shown that the harm in the critically ill vitamin C group did not occur during the time that vitamin C was administered, but immediately after the administration of vitamin C was terminated [4,5]. Thus, the harm was explained by the rebound effect, meaning that it was the sudden discontinuation that caused the adverse outcome. If the scientific question concerns the effect of vitamin C administration on COVID-19, the analysis should distinguish between the period during which vitamin C is given and the follow-up period after its discontinuation.

Xu et al. calculated the effect of vitamin C on ICU stay in Table 2 [1], and found that MD (the mean difference) was 0.86. However, in the text section Xu writes: “*Patients supplemented with vitamin C did not exhibit a prolonged ICU stay (OR = 0.86..*” The OR (odds ratio) is used in the analysis of binary variables, while MD is appropriate for continuous variables. Xu et al. appear to have confused these measures in their calculations.

These and numerous other flaws in Xu et al.’s analysis render the calculated effect estimates unreliable and uninformative.

References

1. Xu W, Wang P, Wan J, Tan Y, Liu Y, Chen Q, Zheng Y, Yu X, Fan S, Jorge Luis CD, Zhang Y. Effect of vitamin C supplementation on outcomes in patients with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Nutr.* 2024 Oct 3;11:1465670.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/39421622>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2024.1465670>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11484096>
2. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2661323>
3. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10600726>
4. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11151746>
5. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11446763>